

**COMPATIBILITY OF LITERATURE WITH THE
ADMINISTRATION SYSTEM AND ECONOMY IN THE WORKS OF
MUKIMI**

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Annotation: This article talks about the poems and ghazals of Muhammad Aminkhoja Mirzakhoja ugli Mukimi, the great poet and thinker of his time, the socio-economic situation of the 19th-20th centuries, and in addition, in these works, the state his attitude and critical thoughts towards the administration and the economy of his time were discussed and analyzed. In addition, the extent to which these critical comic masterpieces and ghazals of Mukimi influenced the state administration and economy is explained in detail.

Key words: Mukimi, his life and work, state administration, literature, economy, economic views, critical thoughts, politics, justice.

Introduction

Literature is the art of words. He strives to find subtle nuances and tones in the human heart and soul, and to reflect them through words. Samples of fiction that can reach the highest level represent the thoughts, experiences, and hopes that stir and excite humanity. Just as people in the world are not alike, so are their emotional experiences. The history of Uzbek literature is rich in masterpieces that skillfully reflect human mental states. They can arouse excitement in the minds and hearts of the current generation and contribute to their spiritual enrichment. Importantly, they are not limited to increasing our educational knowledge, but serve to improve our artistic taste and spiritual maturity.

Muhammad Aminkhoja Mirzakhoja ugli, known by the nickname Mukimi, was born in Kokand in 1850 in a family of intellectuals. He was a witness of a period of social and political upheaval in a certain sense of political change in this area, that is, the region. We can see that the Uzbek poet and thinker was able to use satire and intelligence together to turn the problems of poverty, injustice, and corruption into a positive side, especially the political and economic situation, and turn it into a weapon against these problems.

Literature review

Mukimi's poems, enriched with the politics of his time, occupied a deep place in the hearts of the people and resonated with them. He criticized the government's oppressive actions against the people and was not afraid to speak openly about it. His cartoons such as "Maskovchi boy tarifida", "Veksel", "Viktor Boy" and "Tanobchilar" are cries for reforming society, expressing the pain of the oppressed and their frustration with this system of government.

Chiqib yangi maskovchidan boylar,

Sinar o'tmayin ba'zisin oylar.

These verses in the comic book "Tariff of the Muscovite Boy" after the accession of Central Asia to Russia, the beginning and development of capitalist relations caused the emergence of rich people who go to Moscow to trade, and this is what it is about.

Xususankim eshoni Xodixo'jam,

Yo'q og'zida qarzini vahmida nam.

Here Mukimi moves from universality to particularity, that is, it becomes clearer who this comic exposes. Khodikhoja Eshon was one of the rich people of Kokand at that time, he owned large cotton fields, cotton cleaning factories, stores, and branches of these stores in other regions of Fergana. In addition to the comic strip "The

Muscovite Boy on the Tariff", his character, who often mentions this person in his satires "Veksel", "Viktor Boy" and others, revealed new aspects of his character and was wrapped in satire to the public. presented in the case and exposed the class of exploiters, i.e. the class of property owners who use the property and labor of others, as a full representative.

**Der emishki, o'risga nisfin beray,
Kelar yilga yarmiga muhlat so'ray.
Qachon bo'lmagan gap qabul aylasin,
Muqarra degaykim, pechat boylasin.**

Since the revolution, there have been such agreements between borrowers and lenders, that is, if a person borrows money and cannot repay it within the agreed time period, that is, if he starts working at the expense of his business, his property is confiscated by the moneylenders as collateral, and they "printed" with l and appropriated. Mukimi is talking about this phenomenon that created capitalist relations.

**Netarmiz, debon qistamas el pulin,
–Berurmen, –desa, –so'miga o'n tiyin.**

In this satire, we will see these lines and all of us will be speechless from the usury and corruption of those times. The debtor was obliged to pay the specified amount (rate) of money rent as a bribe (usury) to the moneylender and officials. Usury flourished after the introduction of capitalist relations, resulting in increased indebtedness among the local working people. Responsibility is one of the main problems and themes of the literature of these times.

**Kelib qoldi o'ziga nogah qasam,
Sarih bo'ldi yolg'onligi muttaham.**

In those times, if he sued someone, the law, i.e. Sharia, made the plaintiff

swear an oath to the responsible persons. This issue of oath was one of the worst and unbearable laws of that time. Rich people, big property owners, big landowners used to swear as a weapon to kill ordinary poor local people, many of them, and destroy peasants. That is, with various threats and pressures, they pledged their property worth several times more than their debts as collateral and swore that they would agree to confiscate them if they could not pay off their debts.

Results of research

It would not be an exaggeration to say that these criticisms, wrapped in the garb of open satire, are Mukimi's weapon against the politics of Tsarist Russia. Mukymi's comic books will not bore the reader. Sometimes it makes you laugh, and sometimes it makes you think deeply. The heroes of his comics are certainly not absent in our time. He was able to quickly enter the hearts of the people through his humorous stories. His simple, easy-to-understand comics reflect real-life events. In the hands of the poet, laughter is not rude laughter or just cheerfulness, small humor, but obstacles to backward progress in life, weaknesses and negative signs in the mind and nature of individuals, ugly character and inappropriate behavior. serves the function of condemnation, rebuke, warning.

Discussion

Mukimi's skillful use of images and metaphors adds depth and poignancy to his political commentary. He describes the suffering and the downtrodden in such a way that every person who reads these poems can stand against such injustices and, of course, fight against them, and feel the hardships of those times in spirit.

Moreover, the influence of Mukimi's poems went beyond the borders of Uzbekistan. His poems, ghazals, and humor have been translated into various languages, especially English, German, Russian, Bengali, and Hindi, and have reached literature lovers all over the world. Scholars and lovers of literature continue to analyze his work, appreciating its historical content, social commentary and

economic aspects, political appeal and purely artistic qualities. Koldosh Pardayev, Ghulam Karimov and Said Abdulla are among such enthusiasts.

At a time when Uzbekistan is trying to make its own way in the world literary scene, Mukimi's critical poems and ghazals remain a source of inspiration. His political poetry serves as a beacon that reminds us of the power of opposition and the importance of fighting for social justice.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the poems and ghazals he wrote down are not just writings, but they are an eternal mirror reflecting the constant struggle between oppression, tyranny, corruption and justice and solidarity. Although a century has passed since the creation of these masterpieces, his verses still retain their power and remind us that the struggle for justice and responsibility requires constant effort. As mentioned above, Mukimi's legacy serves as a beacon, that is, language and literature are used as weapons against lies and injustice. urges not to hesitate. Studying the way of life and creativity of this great person not only gives pleasure, but also cognitive knowledge and new knowledge. As a result of each re-search, other new aspects will emerge and ensure that we have the right attitude to justice and public policy of the youth.

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